

DELIVRABLE 9.2

INITIAL COMMUNICATION PLAN

Work Package 9

Dissemination, Exploitation, and Training Activities

30 June 2020

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
ACRONYMES	5
1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
2. INTRODUCTION	7
2.1. Definitions and links with other WPs	7
3. TARGET AUDIENCES (STAKEHOLDER TYPES)	8
3.1. Overview of scales, goals and channels	8
4. CHANNELS OF COMMUNICATION	13
4.1. Internal Communication Flow.....	13
4.2. Project Outlets for Communication & Dissemination materials).....	15
4.3. Training Activities.....	17
4.4. Community Workshops	18
4.5. Community of Practice (COP).....	23
5. EVALUATION	25
6. IMPLEMENTATION	27
7. SUMMARY	30

ACRONYMES

CCT	Coordination Committee Team
COP	Community of Practice
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EC	European Commission
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
SME	Small and medium-enterprise
WP	Work package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The UNITED project requires open channels of communication with many different parties on many different levels. Firstly, internally between the large number of partners, secondly communication flows specific to the communities surrounding and involved with the demonstration pilots, and lastly with external entities that are concerned with the development, deployment, and management of multi-use from the local to international scales. This document outlines the initial communication flow pathways for the project, both internal and external, which is of great importance for a well working consortium and good communication to externals. A continuous dialogue with authorities, administrative bodies and other relevant stakeholders commenced early and it will continue throughout the project in order to enable the smooth implementation of pilots and effective up take of the overall project results. Specific stakeholders, relevant in the context of UNITED demonstration pilots and project activities, have been identified and listed through the efforts of Work Package 5, notably in the outputs of Deliverable 5.1. These specific stakeholders are aggregated into more broad and generalized stakeholder groups with whom the demonstration pilots will engage with on a local and regional levels. The stakeholder lists are further expanded upon to include national, European, and international level actors with whom communication flows of critical outputs, defined in the implementation section of this document, will be employed for effective awareness raising and uptake of project results. This initial communication plan, will be further adapted and enhanced as new stakeholder groups come to light throughout the execution of the project and additional details on specific items of importance for communication to stakeholders are developed through project activities. The final communication plan will reflect these evolutions and be delivered at the end of the project to summarize overall communication actions taken throughout the life of the UNITED project.

2. INTRODUCTION

The UNITED project aims to develop five different ocean multi-use pilots in European seas focusing on multi-use combinations with renewable energy, aquaculture and tourism. Due to the different sectors comprising the multi-use solutions in five pilots, a multitude of stakeholders are considered to provide a better foundation for the research developments on multi-use within the project. The stakeholder classification conducted for this report, considered both internal (project partners and sub-contractors) and external stakeholders. This report presents the initial communication plan and focusses on building a suitable stakeholder foundation for the implementation of the pilots.

In Chapter 6, the description of Channels of Communication can be found. This is divided by the internal (see 4.1) and external communication. Since dissemination and communication of project activities and results is very important for UNITED, several measures will be taken. Besides, training activities, e.g. workshops or webinars are planned which is targeted towards both, internal and external participants.

To be able to make a declaration about the impact of communication activities within UNITED, several indicators have been specified in this report and these will be monitored throughout the project. Additionally, analyses on short-term and medium-term evaluation goals can be found in Chapter 5. The report ends with information about the implementation of the communication plan.

2.1. Definitions and links with other WPs

In UNITED, stakeholders are characterised with regard to their power and influence. The communication with key stakeholder groups in each of the pilot sites will need to be maintained throughout the project in order to avoid possible risks and ensure the support and up-take of project results. Starting the communication early and taking possible concerns into consideration early on will be of utmost importance for the smooth running and success of the project. UNITED Deliverable 5.1, Framework and practical guidelines for stakeholder engagement, identifies key stakeholders that should be involved directly in the UNITED project and provides a description of such stakeholders on a detailed level per pilot through a stakeholder registrar (in a form of an internal excel sheet). Further information on these analysis and registrars can be found in this corresponding deliverable. The communication plan draws on these initial results on stakeholder analysis and generalizes the pilot specific results using consistent terminology in order to develop an overview on the types of stakeholders at various level (local, regional, national, European, and international) and highlights the key information which is identified as relevant to such stakeholders. It also specifies through which contact channels interactions may take place, and what are the key project outputs, deliverables, and activities that would be of interest to different stakeholder categories. The final communication plan, Deliverable 9.8 due at the end of the project, will record the evolution of the communication plan implementation, and detail the extended communication activities undertaken and impacts achieved during the project lifetime.

3. TARGET AUDIENCES (STAKEHOLDER TYPES)

As the UNITED-project is build out of five pillars: technical, regulatory, economic, social and environmental viability, aiming to capture the multiple dimension of marine multi-use activities, it is understood that a diverse array of stakeholders must be considered in order to address each of the pillars. The UNITED project faces two distinct group of stakeholders, those which are internal to the project (i.e. partners, and sub-contractors) and those which are external (i.e. public authorities, insurance companies, design and manufacturing firms not working within the project, as well as the local communities). The stakeholders being directly targeted within the project are addressed through all the work packages, with WP5 and WP9 acting as joint gate keepers to the communication and engagement efforts to minimize stakeholder fatigue. The stakeholders directly involved with the demonstration pilots are listed and aggregated through the efforts of WP5 through close collaboration with the implementation efforts of WP7. Deliverable 5.1 and 1.2 both delve into further details on the particularities and nuances of the internal actors for the UNITED project; the requirements and modes of interaction.

Types of key stakeholders to be engaged in the project:

- **External:** The external stakeholders of the project are those who have not been directly involved in the implementation of pre-operational, operational, or post-operational activities of the demonstration pilots but may be involved in interviews and workshops to advise the activities and research. They are also key actors in the effective dissemination and engagement efforts of the UNITED project to generate a community of practice, come to a consensus on best practices, and expose the results of the activities and lessons learnt through the project activities. This deliverable focuses on these external actors. Thus, the external stakeholders include main users of the project outputs. For example, those are the stakeholders working in industries which would benefit from the pillar outputs (governmental, insurance, implementation companies, etc.). When it comes to public authorities, and other relevant regulatory agencies (e.g. insurance agencies, classification bodies), there are typically one or two stakeholders identified as a liaison/representative of the authority. However, a secondary grouping of stakeholders are businesses actors who would be able to implement lessons learnt in furthering the development of ocean multi-use. Also, there are localized stakeholders related to each of the demonstration pilots which are not directly in contact with the project or activities but impacted by them.
- **Internal:** An internal stakeholder is part of the project team, be it the project partner or the sub-contractor. They are usually interested in the efficiency of project run and may contribute with their knowledge to assist especially for the single pilots. Additionally, grouping of stakeholders around the pilots itself are of internal type, since they are directly required for implementation. The project Advisory Board stakeholders are also categorised as internal.
- **'Expanded' Stakeholders:** These may include the industry, customers, employees, manufacturers, vendors, environmental and other community activists, and more, that may not have direct interest in pilots or may not operate in countries where UNITED pilots are located. These for example include wider associations representing certain industry on the EU/international level, or the international governance bodies and initiatives, or media. Maintaining strong, consistent communications with all types of stakeholders ensures stronger impact through a much more buy-in and better public relations.

The stakeholder groups have been listed and categorized as seen in table 3.1 of this document identifying key group to engage with outside of the project, determining the level of these actors, whether it be those at the local scale, regional, national, European wide, or international which are key target audience members, and generating a preliminary outline of materials and topics of interest already known by UNITED to be relevant to these stakeholder groups. As the project progresses, and principally through the stakeholder workshop and engagement sessions, these materials and topics of interest will be expanded upon and updated to best reflect new developments.

3.1. Overview of scales, goals and channels

Apart from classifying stakeholders according to their sectors and/or field of operation, the scale at which they operate is important as well. As already mentioned before, in relation to the external stakeholders, the scale may vary between local, regional, national, European, and international. Further descriptions of the detailed

stakeholders can be found in Deliverable 5.1, and the following table should be used as a quick-guide for accessing the type of stakeholders that may be encountered in many aspects of the project and clarifies what communication material the project has to offer them. Namely, for each of the stakeholder groups, main communication goals, contact channels and materials are specified in the table 3.1. This table will be amended and enhanced throughout the project in order to best reflect the activities achieved and best define the stakeholders engaged with throughout the project. Thus, this initial tabulation represent the expectations of the consortia at this moment. The full names and delivery time of cited deliverables can be found in the implementation plan under section 6 of this document.

Table 3.1 : Tabulation of the Stakeholder categories with Topics and Materials of Interest

Stakeholder	Example of the type of stakeholder (selection of samples)	Scale [Local, Regional, National, European, International]	Contact Goals and Directives	Contact Channels	Relevant Materials
Energy Park Site Owners	Private Entities, Investment Firms, Collectives	L, R, N, E	Communication of the methods of implementation for Multi-Use, blueprints, tools, benefits, and technologies supporting conversion to multi-use and new developments	SME and Event Networking, Community of Practice, Distribution Mailing Lists	Newsletters, Policy Briefs, Blueprint for Rollout, Pilot fiches, Webinars Deliverables: 1.4, 1.5, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 9.1, 5.5
Energy Park Site Operators	Private Entities, Investment Firms, Collectives	L, R, N, E, I	Operational strategies, technologies, and support tools to effectively work and maximize synergies in the multi-use environment	Networking Events for SMEs and Marine / Offshore Operators, Partner networks, Community of Practice	Blueprint for Rollout, Pilot fiches, Deliverable: 2.1, 2.3, 2.5, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4,
Aquaculture-Site Owners/Operators	Private Entities, Investment Firms, Collectives	L, R, N, E	Communication of the multi-use business opportunities, methods of implementation for Multi-Use, blueprints, and technologies supporting conversion to multi-use and new developments, business models and commercialisation information.	SME and Event Networking, Partner networks, Community of Practice, Distribution Mailing Lists	Newsletters, Pilot fiches, Policy Briefs, Blueprint for Rollout, Webinars Deliverables: 1.4, 1.5, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 9.1, 5.5
Engineering, Design, and Construction Firms	Mariculture, Energy (wind, solar, wave), Structural, Environmental, Construction & Fabrication	L, R, N, E, I	Technological barriers, solutions, and tools to effectively convert, design, and implement multi-use designs, Close relation with WP2	Industry Specific Event via Panel Displays & Presentations, through consortia member networks and partners	Deliverables: 1.5, 2.5, 2.6, 4.4, 7.4, 7.5, 8.5

Offshore Suppliers & Contractors	Shipping & Vessel Companies; Helicopter Agencies, Divers	L, R, N, E	Operational strategies for the day-to-day barriers in operation; technical solutions and support mechanisms to streamline and reap synergies from operations	Consortia Member networks and Partners, Offshore Networking and Development Events, Community of Practice, Training Sessions and Knowledge exchange events	Deliverables: 1.5, 2.5, 2.6, 4.4, 7.4, 7.5, 8.5
Research	Universities, Business Research and Development Branches, Private and National Research Bodies	R, N, E, I	New developments in technologies, combinations, and support systems; Frameworks and methodologies used within the project; Report outputs and publications	Scientific Conferences, Scientific Networks, PhD and Master of Science Students, Partner University Affiliations	Journal Publications, Magazine Publications Deliverables: 1.2, 1.5, 2.1, 2.3, 2.5, 2.6, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 4.4, 5.1, 5.3, 5.5, 7.2, 7.5,
Education	Schools	R, N, E	Practical and Popular Science type materials showcasing developments in the management and operation of maritime activities across sectors		Magazine Articles, News Briefs, Newsletters
Tourist Boards and Councils	Tourist offices, National Tourism boards, tourism associations	L, R, N, E	Information of multi-use business opportunities and added values that the concept may bring to the industry	Conferences, events and showcases, project partner contacts	Newsletters, News briefs Deliverables: 1.5, 2.5, 2.6, 3.4, 3.4, 6.4, 7.5, 8.5
Tourist Venture Companies	Dive Operators, Tour Operators, Fishing Excursions	L, R, E	Information on synergies and practical guidelines for legal, health & safety, and policy guidelines for operating touristic ventures in multi-use sites. Increase awareness about the added values that the multi-use concept may bring to the industry and teach about business models and soft skills needed for venturing into multi-use.	Commercial events and showcases, project partner contacts	Newsletters, News briefs Deliverables: 1.5, 2.5, 2.6, 3.4, 3.4, 6.4, 7.5, 8.5
Insurance Entities	Marine, Liability, Property	R, N, E	Results of the legal, financial, risk, and policy revisions and collaborations resultant of the project	Lloyd's Partner Network, Commercial Expositions, Partner Networks	Webinars, Policy Briefs Deliverables: 1.5, 2.6, 3.4, 6.4, 9.7
European Policy Agencies	EC, JRC, JPI, Better Training for Safer Food (BTSF), European Food Safety Authority	E	Barriers and areas lacking definition in the realm of policy, regulations, and support from such agencies which is	European Commission (EC) and Project Officer networks, partner networks, policy meetings, commission presentations	Policy Briefs, Presentations Deliverables: 1.4, 3.3, 3.4, 4.4, 2.6, 3.4, 6.4, 9.8

	(EFSA), European Wind Energy Association (EWEA), VASAB, OSPAR		hampering Multi-Use Implementation. Summary of societal and business hurdles to overcome to reach adoption of multi-use. Information on environmental and economic impact and potential risks of scaling and wider adoption of Multi-Use		
National policy Agencies	Maritime Spatial Planning Authorities, Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality, Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment, Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management	R, N, E	Barriers and areas lacking definition in the realm of policy, regulations, and support from such agencies which is hampering Multi-Use Implementation. Information on environmental and economic impact and potential risks of scaling and wider adoption of Multi-Use	Partner networks, policy meetings, other projects where agencies are involved (e.g. under Interreg)	Policy Briefs, Presentations Deliverables: 1.4, 3.3, 3.4, 4.4, 2.6, 3.4, 6.4, 9.8
Public	General Public, Local Communities, Local Non-Governmental Organizations, Town Halls	L, R, E	Outreach materials explaining the benefits of multi-use, implications for communities and society at large	Partner networks	Magazine Articles, Newsletters, Webinars
Environmental Non-Governmental Organizations	Environmental Interest Groups	N, E, I	Outreach materials and studies explaining the benefits of multi-use, implications for the environment	Different channels/materials depending on a scale	Journal Articles, Studies and deliverables under the WP.4 i.e. 4.4.
Health and Safety Boards	National and Regional Regulators, Offshore Regulators, Food and Agriculture Regulators	R, N, E	Barriers and areas lacking definition in the realm of Health and Safety policy, and regulations. Information on health and safety impact and potential risks of scaling and wider adoption of Multi-Use	Partner networks	Journal Articles, Studies and deliverables under the WP.6 i.e. 6.4.
Museums	Maritime, Energy, Technology, Engineering, Science	R, N, E	Spreading the awareness about the concept of multi-use as a technology innovation, and sustainable solution for our oceans.	Partner networks	Brochures, posters and flyers

Information & Exhibition Centres	Maritime, Energy, Tourism, Science	L, R, N, E	Spreading the awareness about the concept of multi-use as a technology innovation, and sustainable solution for our oceans.	Partner networks	Information brochures, posters and flyers
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Managing negative feedback

When communicating the project, UNITED aims to always provide the contact information where interested stakeholder can get in touch and express their opinion. The contact information is included on the website contact page, on the flyer, and on all UNITED presentations and videos.

When faced with possible negative feedback or complaint related to UNITED activities or outcomes, as a first level of action the responsible partner will discuss the complaint with the stakeholder and the project lead. As a second level of action, the project CCT will discuss possible mitigation measures, engage the stakeholder in the discussion, and contact the Project Officer for the advice if needed. Identification and engagement of such key stakeholders early on in the project will be crucial in order to allow enough time for possible concerns to be discussed and re-solved, and mitigation measures to be implemented.

4. CHANNELS OF COMMUNICATION

4.1. Internal Communication Flow

4.1.1. Meetings

The UNITED project meetings take place twice a year (depending on the travel restrictions) either in person or via virtual methods in order to ensure open communication flow and synergies between work packages and pilots. Thus, the project will hold a minimum of 8 partner meetings for the duration of the project. The exact date, location and hosting partner for the meeting is always determined at least 2 months in advance of the event. We will aim to hold meetings at/back to back with the major conferences and workshops in order to maximize impact of the project, and make travel efficient.

Apart from the physical all-partner-meetings regular conference calls will be set up mostly bi-monthly, to continually assess project status including risk management, brainstorming and planning of next steps. Meetings of the Coordination Committee Team (CCT) will take place on a monthly or bi-monthly basis; should critical events or situations arise, these will be shifted to bi-weekly until any issues are effectively resolved, then returning to month or bi-monthly depending on require input and the rotating agenda. Such CCT calls are lead by the Consortia, Ghada El Serafy of Deltares. The project leader as well as the leads of the different work packages (WPs) are part of the CCT. These meetings enable an overall management of the WPs. Additionally, risks and raised issues can be discussed as well as connections between single tasks of the different WPs.

Next to the regular CCT meetings, virtual meetings within the WP will take place if necessary. Generally, they approach single deliverables, which have to be discussed with the participants of the task.

Impressions from the project Kick Off meeting

The project started with a face-to-face kick-off meeting in Delft, Netherlands. It was set up by the project coordinator, took place for three days and was very productive. It served to bring all the partners together to explore the current status of the pilots since project inception and proposal construction as well as to align the projected activities to be carried out within the first year with the now active project team across all partners and pilots. The first day of the kick-off was mainly used to introduce all the partners and staff to be working on the project as well as to review the project plan. Additionally, the expectations, objectives and ambitions were clarified just as discussing basic understanding questions. The Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) was also included in the kick-off meeting to introduce these key invited industry and research experts to the overall design, ambitions, and practicalities of the UNITED project implementation. Their advice, drawn from experience in the various sectors exploited within UNITED, and recommendations on pitfalls and solutions, especially in the first years of deployment, served as key notes of discussion; the inclusion of these members begins the expansion of the network of UNITED and development of dissemination channels. The expansion of said network will serve in supporting expert exchanges, and staff of the academic and industrial actors participating directly in the UNITED project and those included through stakeholder engagement, thereby improving the knowledge and skills of those working in the blue growth field across Europe.

4.1.2. Communication Flow

Besides the virtual and physical meetings, several other possibilities are existing to provide a good internal communication between all partners.

Platform Teams

The main platform, which will be used by all consortium members of the project, is Microsoft Teams. This platform includes a chat function (private as well as project-public), to discuss small issues.

E-mail

Besides the platform Teams and phone calls (in very urgent situations) e-mails will still be used, since MS Teams is not useful for including externals.

For a more simplified communication, distribution e-mails are created internal for project use with a master coordination communication email provided by the coordinator, Deltares:

- UNITED-Project@deltares.nl includes all members of the project coordinator at Deltares

4.1.3. Bi-directional communication

To provide a good bi-directional communication between the WP leader of the WPs 2 to 6 with the participants of the WP7 (pilots), questionnaires will be used. To prevent overloading the pilots with double questions and questionnaires, at first one merged questionnaire will be provided from the WP leads to the pilots. In this way, pilots can update the information that they provided in the first place. A second questionnaire with more detailed questions will be created in a later stage. Apart from this, there will also be a questionnaire vice versa: The information that WP7 needs from WP 2 to WP 6.

4.1.4. Bi-Monthly update

Apart from the planned bi-directional communication of the WP7 with the WPs 2 to 6, the pilot leads have to fill in a template monthly, to keep every project partner updated on the actual stage of the pilots. Templates are handed in by the pilot leads at the end of Jan, March, Mai, July, Sep, Nov via the communication platform Microsoft Teams (see Chapter **Error! Reference source not found.**) to the WP7 Lead (FuE). This template includes information about the progress of pre-operational, operational and post-operational phase of the pilot leads. Besides, this monthly update should inform about what the pilots do, their risks and issues, how to solve problems and their next steps. This is especially useful for earlier stage pilots, who can learn from the others. The following main questions are part of the template:

- What were the objectives/activities of the past month?
- What are the objectives/planned activities/tasks of the upcoming month?
- Can all future activities be conducted according to schedule?
- Which topics shall be discussed within the next meeting/phone conference?

4.1.5. Timeline

To enable all participants of this huge project to have an overview of the schedule, all pilot leads fill in a timeline. The schedule within the timeline does not have to be very detailed, but a rough overview of the plan per quarter is developed and maintained for internal purposes. This enables all persons across pilots and WPs to follow progress and upcoming events per pilot.

4.1.6. Due dates of accomplishments

There are several deliverables and tasks which must be accomplished over the course of the next 3.5 years. To arrange a good procedure, the deliverables must be sent to the CCT one month prior their due dates for the submission to the EC. This enables that members of the CCT can review the deliverable within two weeks. Thus, the last two weeks can be used to implement comments and suggestions before the submission to the EC portal.

4.1.7. Communication Platform

As an internal communication platform, Microsoft Teams was chosen due to several reasons:

- Teams is included in the office package, thus almost everyone has access
- Data are accessible on all devices (also via phone)
- Many possibilities included in Teams like: virtual meetings, exchange of documents, chat function and internal calendar to keep track on tasks and deliverables

The main advantage of Teams for the UNITED project is the possibility to share results and internal document. Therefore, documents can be uploaded and downloaded by all participants via SharePoint in an organised and structured way.

For a better structure in Teams for the project, several Channels are existing, as can be seen in Figure 1. Each Channel consists of a chat function for questions, small discussions, shared information or invitation for upcoming

meetings. To remain the chat function in the single Channels structured, it is possible to give a new message a title and reply directly on this message.

Figure 1 – Snapshot of the single channels set up in Microsoft Teams for the UNITED project

Overall, channels are existing for:

- General
- CCT
- Each single WP

The “General” channel is for main questions, files, etc. regarding the overall project. It includes the function of posts, files (overview and a link to SharePoint), a wiki about how to guide and etiquette in Teams, a general planner and scheduling, the website of UNITED (can be opened directly in Teams without an additional web browser) and a structured overview for deliverables and their due dates.

The CCT channel is closed, so only CCT members have access. Posts function, files (overview and a link to SharePoint) and a wiki about basic information of each single WP is included here. A closed channel for the project coordinator is existing as well.

Additionally, channels for each WP can be found in this team. These channels are open for everybody which enables, that every interested project partner can have a look into every single WP. These channels are existing of posts, files (overview and a link to SharePoint), wiki and planner. Note, that the wiki and planner can be filled in by responsible partners and leaders of the particular WP.

4.2. Project Outlets for Communication & Dissemination materials)

The UNITED project focuses on dissemination and communication of project activities and results, with the objective of establishing an ongoing dialogue with potential users and other audiences during the project and beyond.

The first steps of the communication and dissemination activity in UNITED included the establishment of a clear, strong visual identity for the project, including logo, colour palette and graphic style which is unique to the UNITED project. The visual identity was then also applied to other project products, including not only the website but also, for example, deliverable templates. The same approach is foreseen also for other upcoming communication elements including the webinar presentation, flyers, banners, policy briefs, etc.

The main project communication and dissemination outlets are described in the next section including the quantitative dissemination targets per each outlet (where such quantification is applicable):

Project outlets	
Project website	
<p>The UNITED project website has been developed early on in the project following the project visual identity guide. It can be accessed at the following address: https://www.h2020united.eu Apart from serving as a project information medium, the website also aims to serve as an information outlet for the topic of multi-use in a wider sense. As such it will also host the relevant information and news from other projects and activities related to the multi-use in the EU. Website contents will be constantly updated and enriched, hand in hand with project activities and developments.</p>	
Intensity	The website will be updated once every month in order to ensure that all the relevant publications and news are included.
Target	Continuous growth of followers with over 300 followers in the first year, 500 in the second year and more than 600 followers towards the end of the project. At least 7 engagements with each post.
Social Media accounts	
<p>A Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook accounts have been created for the UNITED project under the common handle @H2020UNITED. Posts are normally planned 2 months in advance, while there is also space for posting ad hock as the sporadic news become available in the project.</p>	
Intensity	Twitter and Facebook are scheduled to have approximately 3 posts per week, while LinkedIn is having a bit lower number of posts given that it requires longer texts.
Target	Continuous growth of followers with over 300 followers in the first year, 500 in the second year and more than 600 followers towards the end of the project. At least 7 engagements with each post.
Newsletter	
<p>A project newsletter will be released approximately every 6 months with an aim to inform a wider pool of stakeholders about project activities, engagement opportunities and disseminate deliverables that have been published in the last 6 months. Apart from the direct news from the project, the newsletter also has a section about other relevant news from the network relevant in the context of ocean multi-use. Ideally, the newsletter contains approximately 6 to 8 news which are easy to read, and contain relevant pictures, visuals and links for further information. Annex 1 provides an example of the first UNITED Newsletter which was released on June 19th 2020, using the NewsletterToGo platform. The newsletter is sent to all subscribers and it is posted and permanently stored on the UNITED website.</p>	
Intensity	Once every 6 months i.e. 8 in total
Target	Continuous growth of newsletter subscriptions, with over 200 subscribers in the first year, and over 500 subscribers towards the end of the project.
Webinars	
<p>UNITED will hold user webinars approximately every 6 months in order to disseminate the project results to the wider audience. Webinars will also engage guest speakers from other projects, industry</p>	

<p>representatives and/or public policy. Whenever possible webinars will be co-organised as to ensure maximum impact and strengthen collaboration across multi-use related projects and working groups. Webinars will be organised via the GoToWebinar platform, while other applications may also be used such as Sli.do and Jamboard, for the interactive part of the webinar. Such interactive applications may especially be beneficial for developing live opinion polls, measuring social awareness, and collecting insights for ongoing project activities. The presentations and reports from the webinar will be saved under the UNITED website 'Publications' page and sent to all registrants.</p>	
Intensity:	Once every 6 months i.e. 8 in total
Target	At least 100 stakeholders engaged from each of the categories (i.e. industry, public policy, research)
External Outlets	
<p>Apart from establishing and using the three listed project outlets, UNITED will also use other already established outlets to maximise the dissemination activities, these include but are not limited to:</p>	
Newsletters of relevant associations and networks	
Example	SUBMARINER Network Newsletter, North Sea Farm Newsletter.
Target groups:	Industry (i.e. sectors of the multi-use system), but also wider pool of stakeholders who may be members of such networks, i.e. public authorities, investors.
Professional industry magazines	
Example	Offshore Wind Magazine
Target groups	Those working in sectors that are a part of the UNITED pilots including tourism, offshore wind, solar energy, and aquaculture (be it fish, seaweed or shellfish).
Scientific journals and conference proceedings	
Example	Marine Policy, Coastal Resources
Target groups	Research community
General press media	
Examples	Local TV stations in each of the pilot countries. Such engagements will mainly serve to inform the general public about the multi-use development in pilots and to raise the awareness about the topic.
Target groups	General public, local politicians, and other interest groups.

4.3. Training Activities

Training activities in UNITED consist of internal (project partners) and external (stakeholders) facing activities. In general, the three types of activities will take place, be it internal or external facing:

- 1) Training workshops

- 2) Recorded learning material
- 3) Webinars

4.3.1. Trainings workshops (internal and external facing)

UNITED will organise training workshops throughout the project as presented under the sub-chapter 6.4. Workshops will be held either in person or online, depending on the travel conditions and target audience.

Internal workshops will focus on the needs of UNITED pilots and lack of capacities for certain topics such as stakeholder engagement in pilots, economic assessment application, etc. Such internal workshops will serve to improve knowledge and align all the relevant partners on certain topic.

External workshops will focus on the transfer of knowledge from the UNITED project to stakeholders and across projects. The proposed topics are tentative and reflect the knowledge gaps and needs identified under MUSES project, and across UNITED pilots. Nevertheless, the stakeholder engagement and assessment throughout the project will ensure that this list is updated in order to reflect the most up to date needs in the context of ocean multi-use.

4.3.2. Learning material (external facing)

Each training and user workshop will be accompanied by

- a) **Briefing material** that will be sent to participants prior to the workshop: This may include, but not be limited to the project deliverables, summaries and policy briefs, and reading material and questions for the interactive part of the workshop.
- b) **Recorded learning material** that will be sent to participants and posted on the website post workshop: Apart from the workshop report this material will also include presentations given at the workshop, video recorded lectures and interviews with experts. Such material will be shared not only with participants but also with all those identified as potentially interested in the topic. Modes and methods for such dissemination activity will rely mostly on the project website, social media, partner networks, working groups and associations. Relevant university alumni networks and ongoing courses participants will also be reached out to (Erasmus Mundus Alumni Network). Sharing of such material on learning platforms such as [UDEMY](#) and [MASTERCLASS](#) will also be considered.

4.3.3. Dissemination Webinars (external facing)

Apart from training workshops, the project will also regularly hold user webinars in order to disseminate the project results to the wider audience, and encourage collaboration. Such webinars will also host speakers from other projects, industry representatives and/or public policy. Whenever possible webinars will be **co-organised** as to ensure maximum impact and strengthen collaboration across multi-use related projects and working groups. Webinars will whenever possible **coincide with major project milestones** in order to maximise the dissemination impact.

The first project webinar held of 3 June 2020, focuses on introducing the project and concept of multi-use to the wider audience, discusses some of the first findings of multi-use state of the art analysis and establishes the link with other ongoing multi-use projects.

4.4. Community Workshops

The UNITED workshops will take place in the period between January 2021 and March 2023. The main aim of these events is to engage relevant stakeholders in order to transfer knowledge i.e. 'training workshop', and/or create ownership and encourage up-take of united outputs through co-creation i.e. 'user workshop'. These workshops should ideally, whenever possible, be **combined events** to maximise impact and minimise travels.

There will be at least **five such workshops** throughout the project. These may be organised as multi-day events to accommodate both 1) input to the project throughout the workshop with relevant experts, and 2) communicate with and teach the wider community. For example, the first day of the workshop may be structured as a focus group workshop with invited experts to gather input and exchange across pilots, and the second day may be

structured as a training workshop, where a wider audience would be invited and both lectures, hands on exercises and field trips would be held.

Whenever possible, workshops should be organised **back to back or at major conferences and symposiums** such as Better Off Blue, Aquaculture Europe, Bioeconomy Summit, WindEurope and/or combined with conferences and workshops of other relevant projects (e.g. seaweed project GRASS final conference, workshops of sister project MUSICA, etc.) in order to ensure that the wider audience is reached, and impact is maximised.

4.4.1. Communicating the workshop

The workshop *save the date* will be communicated at least 2 months before the event, in order to avoid potential overlaps with other similar events, and to allow enough time for the critical mass of attendees to form. Each workshop will be promoted via the social media, newsletter, and project website, while additional channels will also be considered depending on the topic, such as newsletters or relevant associations and networks, working groups, etc. Direct invitations will be sent while adhering to the GDPR, to relevant stakeholders in the partnership network. The formation of the advisory board and community of practice will also allow for easier reaching of relevant actors.

4.4.2. Tentative list of workshops

Below is the list of workshops with proposed tentative timing, topic and target audience.

The list of workshops is based on the curriculum prepared in D7.3 and on the report on training workshops for stakeholder engagement in D5.3. Deliverable D7.3 covers training and capacity building of personnel in order to reduce risks as well as to increase safety and efficiency for offshore operations. It is therefore closely linked to the societal engagement in WP5 and thus feeds the planned training and dissemination activities of WP9. The subtask includes the preparation of public awareness materials not only for touristic purposes but also for educational objectives. The educational program is highly important for recruitment of experienced staff for ongoing and future development of multi-purpose industries. Several learning modules are obligatory from the start, including the regulations and legal rules applying to general aspects of: a) Offshore platform operation (e.g. health and safety standards) (all pilots) b) Environmental regulations related to handling and disposal of wastes in an appropriate manner (all pilots) c) Basic knowledge on the biology of target species employed and offshore aquaculture (pilot 1,2,3,5) d) Basic knowledge on aquaculture technology employed in marine offshore farming (pilot 1,2,3,5) e) Handling procedures and management issues of aquaculture offshore systems (e.g. maintenance, stocking, harvesting) (pilot 1,2,3,5) f) Basic knowledge on operational needs for land-based support systems (spare parts logistics, perhaps data processing, further handling of harvest, storage and distribution) (all pilots) g) Basic knowledge on legislation and operation for special support boats (including courses on navigation, safety at sea and other regulatory requirements) (all pilots).

1	Stakeholder engagement training for pilot leads
Facing	Project internal
Aim	<p>The training aims to improve capacities of pilot leads for conducting stakeholder engagement activities to ensure social acceptance of new multi-use developments in pilots, and reduce risks associated with it. Ideally, stakeholders will be included in the pertinent steps in the development process (co-creation) and their wishes and needs will be addressed to propel the design of supported and commercially relevant multi-use platforms. Specifically, the workshop should teach pilot leads about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • methods of stakeholder engagement which may ease the process of pilot implementation and contribute to more informed pilot solutions. Such methods may include focus groups to engage tech innovators to advise on technical solutions for pilots, or interactive meetings with experienced aquaculture farmers to generate ideas for the best choice of species to be farmed, timing, handling of harvest, potential buyers of the harvested product, etc.) • methods for engagement with local communities to help to reduce risks associated with possible complains from local communities (e.g. noise, visual

	impact) and to increase social acceptance of and awareness about upcoming pilot developments. Pilots, especially those working close to shore, need to ensure that the local communities are well informed about the upcoming developments and are communicated potential benefits of multi-use.
Target audience	This training workshop is primarily for a single interlocuter and other relevant + partners working in pilots. Nevertheless, the training can also be formulated in such way so that it is also relevant to external audience. This way, it would contribute to the skills of those 'working in the blue economy' and those who may aim to develop multi-use in the future.
Organisers	WP5 (Acteon/Deltares), WP9 (SUB/Deltares), WP7 (FUE).
Place	Online, due to travel restrictions
Proposed Time	August-November 2020
Note	This workshop is a requirement under the 5.3, 9.2, 7.3 (also relevant under 8.2 e.g. local socio-economic benefits, and under 5.4 which is to measure the changes in the level of social acceptance)

2	Aquaculture multi-use offshore : Technology, environment and biology
Facing	Public
Aim	<p>The workshop aims to improve capacities and knowledge of aquaculture related businesses in the context of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environment: regulations related to handling and disposal of wastes in an appropriate manner; • Technology: focusing on technical challenges and suitable aquaculture technology employed in marine offshore farming. • Biology: Basic knowledge on the target species employed and offshore aquaculture <p>The workshop especially focuses on these actors and topics given that the aquaculture offshore and associated value chain is still a relatively 'young sector' in the EU. The workshop has two parts (i.e. two separate days)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interactive workshop that will allow for the exchange of lessons learned across pilots in the sphere of aquaculture and allow for cross-pilot learning to occur; 2) Workshop to communicate and discuss the project findings in the sphere of aquaculture, and demonstrate work conducted at one of the pilot sites (i.e. field trip). <p>Ultimately, this training workshop aims to raise the awareness and knowledge about multi-use for those working in aquaculture sector.</p>
Target audience	This training workshop is primarily for those working in aquaculture. It is also for pilot leads and other relevant partners working in pilots that deal with aquaculture, and along its value chain.

Organisers	FuE, WINGS, Noordzeeborderij, Seaweed Company, SUB
Suggested Co-Organisers	AWI, AquaBioTech
Place	At the Better of Blue SUBMARINER conference in Sweden (March 22-28, 2021) or at the AQUACULTURE EUROPE or alternatively at a pilot site (any of pilots that have aquaculture NL, BE, DE, GR), back to back with the project partner meeting.
Proposed Time	March-May 2021
Note	This workshop is a requirement under the deliverables D5.3 and D7.3.

3	Offshore Platform Operation & Safety
Facing	Public
Aim	<p>The workshop aims to improve knowledge transfer in the context of health and safety standards for offshore platform operation and multi-use logistics. The workshop may focus on questions such as What are safety requirements of a multi-use offshore platform?</p> <p>The workshop has two parts (i.e. two separate days)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interactive workshop that will allow for the exchange of lessons learned across pilots which work with offshore platforms and allow for cross-pilot learning to occur; 2) Hands on training that will communicate the project findings related to safety of offshore platforms and related logistics, and demonstrate work conducted at one of the pilot sites (i.e. field trip to the Danish offshore wind farm platform – people can climb to the top nacelle and learn about safety procedures). <p>Ultimately, this training workshop aims to raise the awareness and knowledge about multi-use for those working in offshore construction/operations (i.e. offshore wind/aquaculture/hydrogen storage/solar) and logistics i.e. boat operators and maintenance.</p>
Target audience	This training is primarily for those working in offshore construction, operation and safety. It is also for pilot leads and other relevant partners working in pilots that deal with offshore platforms. It may also be relevant for certification bodies, and regulators.
Organisers	FUE, SPOK, HYDRO, LR
Suggested Co-Organisers	MARIN, PLOCAN, MAREI
Place	Ideally, it should be organised together with the Space@Sea project final conference. Space@Sea focuses on offshore multi-use platforms. It should also be combined with PLOCAN and MUSICA work with both focus on actual multi-use platforms. Workshop to be co-organised with PLOCAN, Space@Sea and MUSICA. Or organised at the Danish pilot site with the field trip.
Proposed Time	September-December 2021

Note	This workshop is a requirement under the deliverables D5.3, D7.2 and D7.3.
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4	Multi-use logistics
Facing	Public
Aim	<p>The workshop aims to discuss questions such as What kind of vessel used for multi-use – i.e. both for aquaculture and offshore wind?; Can some of the operations and maintenance activities be combined in a multi-use system? This also includes legal aspects in the context of logistics</p> <p>The workshop has two parts (i.e. two separate days)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Basic knowledge on operational needs for land-based support systems (spare parts logistics, perhaps data processing, further handling of harvest, storage and distribution) 2) Interactive workshop that will allow for the exchange of lessons learned across pilots with special engagement of charterers, boat operators ; 3) Hands on training that will communicate the project findings related to efficiency and safety of logistics, and opportunities for combined operations and maintenance (aquaculture boat used for OWF maintenance/monitoring), and demonstrate work conducted at one of the pilot sites.
Target audience	This training is for ocean business community (aquaculture farmers, offshore platform operators), and certification bodies, regulators.
Organisers	Deltares, FUE, other partners depending on interest and concrete topics addressed
Suggested Co-Organisers	WindEurope
Place	At the WindEurope conference
Time	September-December 2022
Note	This workshop is a requirement under the deliverable D7.3.

5	Multi-Use Business Cases and Economics
Facing	Public
Aim	<p>The workshop aims to discuss UNITED business cases with potential users and other relevant stakeholder in order to generate ideas and maximise socio-economic benefits of multi-use solutions resulting from UNITED pilots. Following are some of the questions that this workshop will consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to market and exploit multi-use products and create added benefits for both sectors and local communities?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are some transferable benefit sharing models that can be applied in the context of multi-use (i.e. cooperative ownership)? • How to create the market pull/push for different multi-use solutions present in UNITED pilots? • Economics: how to derive benefits for both sectors and encourage multi-use. <p>This workshop will encourage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • exchange of lessons learned across pilots with special engagement of marketing and business experts; • communication of project findings related to business opportunities and exploitation of multi-use products and services (e.g. multi-use certification, shared ownership structures). <p>The workshop will also contribute to the Commercialisation roadmap, which is one of the final main products of the UNITED project.</p>
Target audience	Industry actors, distributors, retail businesses, investors in relevant sectors (aquaculture, solar, wind energy, tourism)
Organisers	SUBMARINER, Seaweed Company, Colruyt
Suggested Co-Organisers	In conjunction with some of the BlueInvest events, accelerators or similar business development and business innovation events and initiatives. Alternatively, it may be split into smaller workshops each focusing on a specific sector.
Place	At the BlueInvest event or relevant DG MARE event. Back to back with one of the project partner meetings.
Time	January-March 2023
Note	

4.5. Community of Practice (COP)

UNITED will work to establish the *multi-use community of practice* that can collaborate throughout the project and continue this collaboration beyond the UNITED project. UNITED engagement activities such as workshops, interviews, webinars and joint development and review of outputs will serve to collect interest and first ideas for establishing such community. The initial phase has already been achieved by connecting to the existing Dutch COP. Through this initiative, the stake in multi-use will be enhanced and broadened in order to engage with the other regional European Seas. To do so, the outreach and communication activities will begin building on such a group through inclusion of specifically targeted webinars and group meetings (either virtually or in person, dependant on capacity). The momentum and connections developed along the lifetime of the UNITED project will be bundled into a stand-alone COP which will represent one of the legacy elements of the project and carry forth the final findings, good will, communication channels, and connections developed through the realization of the project work.

The UNITED website will have an important role in the formation and functioning of the community. It shall serve as a multi-use information gateway, including the multi-use FAQ section, examples and lessons learned from various multi-use related projects and interactive discussion pages. We aim to engage a wider multi-use community that would contribute to the updates of the platform in terms of multi-use related data, information, journal papers and pilots, beyond the UNITED project, and collaborate on organisation of joint events and future development opportunities in the context of multi-use.

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement no 862915

UNITED partners, many of them who have been involved in multi-use related projects in the past and/or who are now involved in multi-use activities in their countries, will also contribute by suggesting suitable members of the community and support the wider dissemination and outreach of the community.

This network will make use of the existing Stakeholder Advisory Board, Dutch COP, and Regional Waters initiatives in bringing together a community focused on the realization of Multi-Use.

5. EVALUATION

The impact of the project's communication activities will be measured using indicators and targets as specified in 4.2 Project Outlets sub-chapter. Such measurements may include the number of visitors of the UNITED website, subscriptions to the newsletter, social media post engagements. The project will also be using feedback polls filled out by workshop participants to receive the feedback on the communication and dissemination performance in the project and stakeholders' satisfaction (i.e. do they feel informed enough and is the content relevant to their interest). This way the project will receive a better understanding of how effective the individual means of communication are in establishing and expanding an accurate understanding of multi-use to the general public as well as to the trained personnel. The following table includes the overall project evaluation goals, objectives, targets and indicators and explains how the communication activities link to these.

Short Term Evaluation Goals	Objective	Targets & Indicators
Raise societal awareness, involve local communities and secure acceptance of these new developments by society-at-large.	Utilize a 3-pointed stakeholder engagement process: (1) a stakeholder analysis in which relevant stakeholders will be identified, (2) inclusion of stakeholder in the pertinent steps in the pilot development process and (3) utilizing stakeholders needs to propel the design of multi-use activities	Indicator: Percentage of stakeholder group activation Target: 75% or higher stakeholder inclusion (of all identified) in all engagement processes across all pilots
	Carrying out training and capacity building of personnel to reduce risks and increase social acceptance and awareness. Webinars will also take place to ensure wider transfer and uptake.	Indicator: Number of workshops, trainings, and capacity building activities. Target: 3 or more instances of webinars and workshops / trainings during the project
	Ecosystem building and stakeholder empowerment through continuous dialogue with authorities, administrative bodies and local outreach activities will be organised with links established amongst relevant intermediaries on the local level, including networks, boards, chambers, associations, forums, etc.	Indicator: Number of stakeholder workshops and empowerment sessions Target: 3 or more instances over the life of the project
	Staged roll out of products and services resulting from pilot work and the project as a whole, linking with implementation roadmap, life cycle assessments, new products and added value services. This rollout is accompanied by a strong marketing campaign to generate interest of potential consumers and society-at-large.	Indicator: Visitors to website. Followers on social media platforms. Number of commercial contacts for support. Number of marketing events. Target: 2 or more marketing events to attract commercial interest. 5 or more commercial contact seeking support to utilize outputs.
	Wider community outreach to increase the awareness about and interest in the topic of multi-use.	Indicator: Number of newsletters, flyers and briefs, press releases. Target: 6 or more newsletters, 3 or more flyers, 3 or more briefs, 2 or more press releases.

Medium Term Evaluation Goals	Activities to Deliver	Targets & Indicators
<p>Improve the professional skills and competences of those working and being trained to work within the blue economy.</p>	<p>Hosting training workshops for stakeholder processes in each pilot (for partners and pilot coordination) about principles and process, adaptation to each pilot, including innovative forms of facilitation using participatory methods to engage participants. Demonstration sessions will also take place online via webinars as to ensure wider transfer and take-up.</p>	<p>Indicator: Number of workshops, trainings, and capacity building activities. Number of Webinars</p> <p>Target: 3 or more instances of both webinars and workshops/trainings over the life of the project</p>
	<p>In 'young' sectors (aquaculture, solar power), the main aim will be to increase soft skills related to commercialisation, budgeting and acquisition of funds, insurance, permitting, etc.</p>	<p>Indicator: Number of training workshops including young sectors</p> <p>Target: 2 or more workshops before the end of the project lifecycle.</p>

6. IMPLEMENTATION

Many of the communication elements are centred around either workshops, training sessions, publications, or deliverables as outlined in sections 3 and 4. With the deliverables, there is a clear delivery date on the publication of these information sources. Additionally, as noted in section 6.2, regularly noted periodic dissemination of project updates, newsletters, and other communication materials. As the trainings and workshops are dependent on a multitude of factors, including participant availability, internal project developments and timelines, as well as other factors which are beyond the control of project partners, guideline objective dates have been provided in sections 4.3 and 4.4. These dates will be concretized in this living document which will form the basis of the final communication plan. For the concretized deliverables which will serve to facilitate knowledge transfer per stakeholder group, as noted in Table 3-1, the deliverable titles and publication dates can be found in Table 6.1 below. The exact date at which they are made public is subject to the time it takes for validation via the EC to certify acceptance of said deliverables. This is in order to ensure only one final version of such communication materials are presented to stakeholder groups.

All project partners are responsible for implementing the dissemination activities on the national level, led by the WP9 leads. On the local level pilots will develop their local stakeholder networks, facilitate outreach and training materials, and translate material into the local language where needed.

Table 6-1 : Implementation Deadline of the Deliverables for Dissemination

Deliverable	Title	Due Date	WP Responsible	Task Responsible	Partner Responsible
2020					
1.2	Report on the State of the art implementation of an integrated pilot approach	2020-06-30	1 - WINGS	1.2	WINGS
5.1	Framework and practical guidelines for stakeholder engagement	2020-07-31	5 – ACT	5.1	WINGS
3.2	UNITED Assessment Framework to Determine Economic Feasibility of Multi-Use Platforms	2020-12-31	3 - ECO	3.2	Ecologic
2021					
7.2	Developing a blueprint for the offshore site operation	2021-04-30	7 – FUE	7.1	KMF
7.3	Curriculum for offshore course, guideline and learning manual	2021-04-30	7 – FUE	7.1	UGent
4.2	Assessment Framework to Determine Ecological Feasibility of Multi-Use Platforms	2021-07-31	4 – UGE	4.2	RBINS
2.1	Toolbox for data analysis, visualization, and planning for decision makers	2021-12-31	1 – WIN	2.1	CONTROS

2.3	Automation and scheduling tools	2021-12-31	2 – DEL	2.3	HIDROMOD
2022					
7.4	Joint production, monitoring, operation and maintenance protocol	2022-06-30	7 – FUE	7.2	KMF
2.5	Decision Support System (DSS) specifications and design for MUCLs	2022-06-30	2 – DEL	2.5	WUR
7.5	Report on harmonized findings from pre-operational and operational phase	2022-08-31	7 – FUE	7.3	UGent
3.3	Assessment on the added value of MUCLs within pilots	2022-12-31	3 – ECO	3.3	RBINS
5.3	Report on training workshops for stakeholder engagement	2022-12-31	5 – ACT	5.2	FUE
3.4	The Business Case for Multi-Use Platforms: Costs, Benefits and Lessons from Practice	2022-12-31	3 – ECO	3.4	WUR
4.4	Environmental Impact Assessment models for the commercial rollout of Multi-Use Platforms	2022-12-31	4 – UGE	4.4	Ecologic
8.5	Implementation Plan for the operation and maintenance	2022-12-31	8 – RBINS	8.5	NSIL
2023					
9.1	Final dissemination report	2023-05-30	9 – SUB	9.1	ACTeon
9.3	Final report on ecosystem building and stakeholders empowerment	2023-05-30	9 – SUB	9.2	Deltares
9.5	Report on training sessions for knowledge transfer	2023-05-30	9 – SUB	9.3	WINGS
1.4	UNITED Framework design	2023-05-30	1 – WIN	1.4	Deltares
6.4	Manuscript of Synthesis of Risk Governance	2023-05-30	6 – WUR	6.4	UGent
9.6	Report on training sessions for technology transfer	2023-05-30	9 – SUB	9.6	UGent

1.5	Catalogue of multi-use blueprint solutions	2023-05-30	1 – WIN	1.5	SUBMARINER
5.5	Recommendations for successful stakeholder involvement in multi-use platforms	2023-05-30	5 – ACT	5.5	RBINS
9.7	Commercialization roadmap	2023-05-31	9 – SUB	9.5	SUBMARINER
2.6	Technical report on design procedure limitations and improvements	2023-05-31	2 – DEL	2.6	WINGS
9.8	A final communication report	2023-05-31	9 – SUB	9.8	SUBMARINER
3.4	The business case for Multi-Use Platforms: Costs, Benefits and Lessons from Practice	2023-05-31	3 – ECO	3.4	WUR

7. SUMMARY

As the UNITED project investigates co-location on five different pilots in European seas with regard to renewable energy, aquaculture and tourism, the number of stakeholders and variety thereof, both internal and external, makes for an extensive network to engage. Adding further complexity to this situation is the breadth of UNITED, covering five critical pillars for multi-use adoption and implementation: technical, regulatory, economic, social and environmental viability, and geographic distribution over 3 regional seas and 5 countries. This generates a wide variety in the internal and activated project stakeholders but also creates a unique opportunity to draw on such activated stakeholders to further reach out and engage with and share knowledge with external stakeholders who are also in the fields represented by internal stakeholders.

The UNITED project faces two distinct group of stakeholders, those which are internal to the project (i.e. partners, sub-contractors,) and those which are external (i.e. public bodies, insurance companies, design and manufacturing firms not working within the project). The stakeholders being directly targeted within the project are addressed through all of the work packages, with WP5 acting as gatekeeper to create semblance and unity in the approach towards the wide array of internal and external stakeholders supported by WP9s communication, dissemination and training activities towards the generation, distribution, and support potential for engagement and dissemination of project related findings. The stakeholders directly involved with the demonstration pilots are listed and aggregated through the efforts of WP5 through close collaboration with the implementation efforts of WP7. Deliverables 5.1, 3.1, and 1.2 both delve into further details on the particularities and nuances of the internal actors for the UNITED project, the express needed and mode of interaction and engagement thereof. This communication plan serves as a reference and guide to interacting not only with the internal stakeholder, identifying key communication and dissemination materials and activities, but has been generalized to contain the external stakeholder groups which will be encountered and engaged with over the coming 3 years of project activities.

This initial communication plan specifies communication and dissemination outlets, target groups, intensity of communication activities and targets. The impact of the project's communication activities will be measured using specified targets and indicators such as the number of visitors of the UNITED website, subscriptions to the newsletter, social media post engagements as well as by using feedback polls filled out by workshop participants. This way the project will receive a better understanding of how effective the individual means of communication are in establishing and expanding an accurate understanding of multi-use to the general public as well as to the trained personnel. By synching the efforts of WP5 and WP9, the efficiency and breadth of stakeholder engagement and information dissemination through the proper channels is believed to be maximized, targeting the most relevant communication materials at the appropriate stakeholders.